

Infrastructure-less UWB-based Relative Localization: an Active Approach

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Abstract—In multi-robot systems, relative localization is crucial in many tasks, such as leader following, target tracking, or cooperative maneuvering. Current approaches either rely on infrastructure-based or on infrastructure-less setups. The former typically achieve high localization accuracy but require fixed external structures. The latter provide more flexibility, but often requires Line-of-Sight (LoS) devices like cameras or lidars. Ultra Wide Band (UWB) devices are emerging as a viable alternative to build infrastructure-less solutions that do not require LoS. These approaches directly deploy the UWB sensors on the robots. However, they require that at least one of the platforms is static, limiting the advantages of an infrastructure-less setup. In our ongoing work [1], we remove this constraint and introduce an active method for infrastructure-less relative localization. Our approach allows the robot to adapt its position to minimize the relative localization error of the other platform.

I. INTRODUCTION

Localization is a longstanding goal in robotics and is certainly one of the most crucial components of every robotic platform. At a high level, localization can be achieved by relying either on a fixed infrastructure or solely on onboard robot sensors. The former setup is implemented by coupling external sensors with onboard markers or receivers. Infrastructure-less solutions, on the other hand, do not require external structure at fixed known positions.

Relative localization between platforms can be exploited to refine their respective global pose estimate, or used for tasks where platforms are mainly interested in their relative pose with respect to another robot. Relative localization can be achieved with various sensor setups, among which the most popular are based on cameras, lasers, and lidars. Despite the impressive results achieved, these approaches suffer from two important limitations: i) relative pose information needs to be inferred from data through perception algorithms; ii) they require Line-of-Sight (LoS) to operate.

Ultra Wide Band (UWB) technology is currently flourishing as a viable alternative to achieve relative localization. UWB systems are cost-effective, can be used to directly access distance information between entities, and can work in Non-Line-of-Sight (NLoS) conditions. Most of the UWB-based solutions are infrastructure-based, *i.e.*, they use fixed UWB sensors with known positions (namely the *anchors*) to localize the platform equipped with another UWB device (often referred to as *tag*) [2].

Recently, UWB sensors have been also employed in infrastructure-less configurations to achieve relative localiza-

Fig. 1: Overview of the proposed approach. Contrary to the SotA approaches (bottom figure with red bar), we develop an active method (top figure with green bar) that exploits the movement of the robot to enhance the localization performance.

tion between robots [3], [4]. In this case, also the anchors are mounted on a mobile platform that estimates the relative position of the robot with the tag UWB. However, most of the State-of-the-Art (SotA) approaches keep the robot with anchors in a fixed position, limiting the advantages of an infrastructure-less setup. Additionally, in infrastructure-less setups the tag moves outside the convex hull delimited by the anchors. In practice, this translates in a worse Geometric Dilution Of Precision (GDOP) [5], a metric that models the localization errors depending on the anchor-tag arrangement. In some configurations, particularly those where the tag is outside the anchor hull, small measurement errors might result in large relative position errors.

Driven by the aforementioned considerations, the purpose of this research is to build an infrastructure-less UWB-based relative localization approach that overcomes the drawbacks of SotA solutions. In particular, we develop an *active* localization method that enables the robot with the anchors to adapt its position to reduce the relative localization error of the tag robot, see Fig 1. This is achieved by training a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) agent that controls the platform to minimize a loss function based on the GDOP metric and on a measurement model tailored to the specific problem we consider. Differently from other solutions, we do not assume that the robot with the anchors is static.

II. METHODOLOGY AND TASK DETAILS

The objective of the proposed active relative localization method is to provide a robotic platform with a suitable

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TABLE I: Results of the simulation experiments. From top to bottom we consider different *AnchorBot - TagBot* initialization distances: 70 cm, 100 cm and 200 cm. The mean μ and the standard deviation σ of the localization RMSE in cm are reported.

Method	Static <i>TagBot</i>						Dynamic <i>TagBot</i>					
	Front Spawn		Side Spawn		Behind Spawn		Straight Line		Circle		Square	
	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
SUL-EQ [6]	11.0	7.8	12.9	9.6	16.0	13.9	28.2	24.9	13.3	10.4	21.6	18.2
SUL-IS	10.3	7.1	12.9	9.7	21.6	30.7	26.0	22.8	13.5	14.1	20.2	16.9
AUL-EQ	11.5	8.1	11.7	8.3	11.5	9.3	12.7	9.1	11.4	8.0	11.9	8.5
AUL-IS (Our)	10.7	7.5	11.0	7.8	11.3	9.7	11.7	8.3	10.6	7.4	11.1	7.8
SUL-EQ [6]	15.9	11.7	18.2	13.7	20.7	15.7	33.3	28.3	18.3	13.7	26.2	21.6
SUL-IS	14.9	10.7	18.0	13.6	20.2	19.5	31.0	26.2	17.7	14.1	24.4	20.0
AUL-EQ	12.0	8.7	12.6	9.5	12.9	9.8	13.1	9.5	12.2	8.7	12.3	9.0
AUL-IS (Our)	11.2	8.0	11.9	9.0	12.3	9.8	12.1	8.7	11.3	7.9	12.1	8.7
SUL-EQ [6]	33.2	25.2	35.6	27.1	37.9	29.0	50.7	41.0	35.6	27.1	42.8	33.9
SUL-IS	30.8	23.1	35.6	27.1	35.3	27.4	47.0	37.7	34.3	26.2	39.7	31.3
AUL-EQ	21.0	17.9	22.7	19.5	24.5	20.6	25.4	20.1	13.3	10.3	17.5	16.6
AUL-IS (Our)	19.5	16.6	23.9	20.4	22.5	19.3	23.8	18.6	12.2	9.4	15.9	15.1

control policy so that to obtain the best possible estimation of another robot position. In this research, we consider an infrastructure-less context with two distinct robotic platforms: the first one, named *AnchorBot*, is equipped with three UWB anchor nodes, and its function is to localize with respect to its body frame the second one, referred to as the *TagBot*, which is equipped with a single UWB tag. The *AnchorBot* have access only to the relative distances between the anchors and the tag, and the goal is to adapt its position in order to minimize the *TagBot* localization error.

To this aim, we propose a new framework that i) study and design an anchor arrangement to adapt the GDOP to the relative localization task in mobile robot scenarios and ii) exploits this design through an active localization strategy.

a) *Anchors Displacement Analysis:* we conduct an in-depth anchor placement analysis to identify suitable configuration for the active localization task. When the *AnchorBot* is static and the *TagBot* moves freely, the best strategy is to keep the GDOP as low as possible at all points surrounding the *AnchorBot*. [6] finds out that the equilateral triangle arrangement comes closest to achieving this goal. However, a uniformly distributed GDOP results in a higher minimum value compared to configurations tailored for localizing the robot within specific areas. Consequently, through an extensive Monte Carlo simulation campaign over a set of possible configurations, we select an isoscele triangle configuration for the anchors. The trade-off is that the *AnchorBot*'s front region hosts the GDOP minimum, requiring precise localization of the *TagBot* in that zone.

b) *UWB Relative Localization Loss:* In an UWB-based localization context, directly using the GDOP as the loss function might seem a reasonable choice since, by definition, it is a performance metric for positioning. However, this is impractical since, in an infrastructure-less scenario, the GDOP minimum falls in the *AnchorBot* footprint area. Furthermore, another aspect that influences localization performance is distance: UWB sensors are not able to provide a reliable measurement for short distances. Consequently, we develop a novel *UWB Relative Localization Loss* that combines the GDOP metric with a suitable measurement model for the anchors that takes into consideration the UWB performance degradation for short ranges.

c) *Deep Reinforcement Learning controller:* for the implementation of the control policy we employ a DRL strategy that leverages Deep Neural Network (DNN) approximators. In particular, we design two DNN architectures: the

actor one learns the optimal policy and only leverages range measurements coming from UWB-devices, while the *critic* counterpart is fed with more privileged information and used only during training phase to evaluate such a policy. For the optimization, we design a suitable reward function based on the UWB Relative Localization Loss.

III. EXPERIMENTS

The proposed **AUL-IS** (Active UWB-Localization - **I**soscele triangle configuration) approach is tested through an extensive simulation campaign and validated with real-world experiments on a wheeled robotic platform. More specifically, we perform two distinct types of experiments. In the first one, the *TagBot* remains stationary and assumes three different positions: in front of, to the side, and behind the *AnchorBot*. The second set of tests is, instead, aimed at assessing the capability of the proposed active method to localize a moving platform. As a comparison baseline, we employ (i) the method proposed in [6] where the *AnchorBot* is kept stationary and the anchors have an equilateral triangle configuration (**SUL-EQ**), (ii) a stationary *AnchorBot* with our isosceles triangle configuration (**SUL-IS**) and (iii) an active version of [6] (**AUL-EQ**).

The results of the simulated experimental campaign are reported in Table I. A first key finding is that the active approaches **AUL-EQ** and **AUL-IS** outperform their static counterparts **SUL-EQ** and **SUL-IS** in every situation. This result is a direct consequence of the control policy developed by the DRL agent, which is able to effectively move and orient the *AnchorBot* so as to maintain the *TagBot* in low GDOP areas. Moreover, it can be observed that the specialized anchor configuration exploited by **AUL-IS** can further enhance the localization performance.

Real-world experiments are carried out to validate the results obtained in the simulation campaign and to demonstrate the transferability of the DRL controller on a real platform. The trained DRL policy is directly deployed on the real *AnchorBot* without any fine-tuning, demonstrating strong generalization capabilities and achieving remarkable localization performance even when real robotic platforms and UWB sensors are involved. The numerical experiments show that **AUL-IS** outperforms **SUL-IS** in each considered scenario, validating what we observed in the simulations experiments.

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